

ISSN - 0974-2719

Indian Journal of Community Psychology

An official Publication of the
Community Psychology Association of India

Volume 9

Issue II

September, 2013

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A Study of Self-Presentation Tactics, Anxiety, Personality and Socio -Demographic Variables of College Girls

Suruchi Bhatia* and G. Bhardwaj**

This study examined the relations among Self-Presentation Tactics, Personality factors like Extraversion, Neuroticism and Anxiety levels of 186 girls in the age range of 18-24 years residing in Delhi and NCR. Self Presentation Tactics scale (SPT); completed by Lee et al, 1999 MPI; by Jalota and Kapoor (1965) and SCAT developed by Sinha and Sinha (1995) were used. Statistical analysis was carried out using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, ANOVA and t-test. Results suggest that all the Self Presentation Tactics were highly inter-correlated except Apology. Extraversion was only related to Apology. But Neuroticism was related to most of the Self Presentation Tactics except Apology, Exemplification and Extraversion. The socio- cultural/ demographic variables generating significant differences among participants were: Family income, Financial status, Father's education, Only child, Mother home maker and Father house husband

Key Words: Self-Presentation Personality Extraversion Introversion Anxiety Demographic Variables

INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive world apart from having good credentials it's important for everyone to present oneself in ways that can have appropriate impact on one's surroundings. As Goffman 1959; Leary, 1995; Schlenker, 2005 found that an inescapable fact of everyday life is the need to "present well" or to make a good impression on others referred to as self presentation or impression management. Self-presentation has sometimes been distinguished from impression management which has been defined as an attempt to control the images presented to others usually to increase the power of the individual. However, as the tactics used to engage in impression management and self-presentation are the same and it is the tactics we are concerned with here, we will use the terms interchangeably as others have done (see Leary and Kowalski, 1990). Self presentation behaviours have often been explained underlying need and motives. The need to be liked, for example, manifests in ingratiating behaviour, where as the need to be seen as blameless from excuses. Lee, Quigley, Nesler, Corbett, and Tedeschi (1999) categorized 12 of the most studied self presentation tactics as defensive or assertive based on previous work by Tedeschi and

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